

Crack Detection on 3D Surfaces Reconstructed from Drone Images of Wall Paintings

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Abstract. Preserving wall paintings is a critical aspect of cultural heritage conservation, requiring precise methods for detecting and monitoring surface damage. This paper presents a methodology for crack detection on wall paintings using structure from motion to reconstruct 3D models from drone-acquired images. High-curvature regions suggestive of cracks are identified through normal vector analysis and curvature computation, followed by binary dilation to improve the segmentation. The method highlights cracks effectively while ensuring accuracy and scalability. The results show a strong correlation between detected cracks and visible damage, showcasing the potential of this approach for non-invasive monitoring and conservation-restoration planning.

Keywords: Crack detection, wall paintings, SFM, surface, drone, monitoring

1. Introduction

The preservation of cultural heritage is essential to ensure that its legacy is sustained for future generations. Due to its importance, an effective conservation strategy requires a multidisciplinary approach that incorporates various scientific and technological methodologies [1 - 3]. This strategy typically involves an in-depth understanding of the object of cultural heritage, which includes its condition, historical background, and structural integrity, achieved through information-based analysis and the use of advanced diagnostic and computational techniques. In addition, it includes the selection and application of appropriate conservation-restoration techniques, which involve the development of materials, tools and methodologies designed to reduce or even reverse the deterioration process. Furthermore, continuous monitoring and validation of conservation measures are crucial, to evaluate their efficiency and ensure the long-term preservation of heritage objects [3].

Among the various types of cultural heritage wall paintings have a particular significance, as they frequently serve as historical records of architectural evolution [4]. These artistic creations, often incorporated into buildings, are vulnerable to environmental degradation due to exposure to climatic conditions [5]. As a result, continuous monitoring and documentation are essential to understanding their current condition and planning effective preservation strategies. The application of drone-based imaging has transformed the study and conservation of wall paintings, by providing an accurate, non-intrusive method for capturing high resolution images [6, 7]. This technology enables detailed documentation of wall paintings, even in inaccessible locations, making it an invaluable tool for conservation initiatives. By acquiring images from multiple angles and elevations, drones provide conservation specialists with a comprehensive dataset for detailed analysis. Using successive images over time, researchers can track structural changes, such as crack development and progress, helping to evaluate the long-term efficacy of restoration efforts [8]. This approach not only reinforces the sustainability of conservation practices, but also contributes significantly to the continued preservation of cultural heritage for future generations.

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For this purpose, the methodology presented in this paper focuses on the detection of cracks on wall paintings using 3D models generated from drone-captured images. Within this context, the following contributions of the paper can be highlighted:

- Innovative approach to detecting cracks through curvature analysis of 3D-reconstructed surfaces from wall paintings.
- Non-invasive and scalable method for monitoring the structural integrity of wall paintings over time.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work in the field. Section 3 details the methodology applied in this study. The results obtained using the proposed approach are presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 summarises the findings and provides concluding remarks.

2. Related Work

The conservation of wall paintings has been studied due to their vulnerability to environmental and structural degradation. Traditional conservation methods include the use of protective layers and climate control to reduce degradation rates [9]. Recent advances in imaging technologies have improved conservation efforts by enabling non-invasive diagnostics and monitoring. D'Agostino and Fabbri [10] used hyperspectral and multispectral images for the identification of pigments and the detection of previous restorations. Additionally, digital photogrammetry and laser scanning have become essential for creating accurate 3D models of wall paintings, supporting both documentation and virtual restoration [11]. Artificial Intelligence and machine learning techniques have also been applied in the conservation of cultural heritage, particularly for the automated detection of degradation patterns. Crack detection and segmentation using deep learning algorithms allow for more precise monitoring of structural changes in wall paintings, as shown by Li et al. [12]. These computational approaches, when integrated with traditional methods, enhance the efficiency and precision of conservation practices.

The detection and monitoring of surface cracks in wall paintings is crucial to assess their long-term preservation status. Manual inspections, though relied upon historically, are time consuming and subject to inconsistencies. Recent research by Barni et al. has shown that thermal imaging and structured light scanning provide a highly accurate means of detecting surface deformations and underlying structural weaknesses [13]. Advanced computational models have also been used for crack analysis. Cornelis et al. [14] have proved that Bayesian approaches for automated crack detection are effective in analysing high-resolution multimodal images of paintings. Furthermore, Sidorov and Hardeberg [15] have explored the representation of crack patterns using graph-based methods, which enable the classification and progression analysis of cracks over time. Recent advances have introduced deep learning-based methodologies for crack detection in building structures, enhancing real-time monitoring capabilities [16]. Moreover, the integration of multiband photogrammetry [17] and hybrid image analysis has provided comprehensive information on the material composition and degradation phenomena of wall paintings. The application of UAV [3] photogrammetry has also facilitated efficient 3D modelling and mapping of cultural heritage sites, contributing to improved preservation strategies. Drone technology has recently been introduced in [18] to monitor the degradation of wall paint over long periods. UAV-based photogrammetry enables conservators to perform frequent high-resolution inspections with minimal interference, thus improving the long-term assessment of conservation efforts.

3. Methodology

The proposed methodology consists of three main steps. First, Structure from Motion (SfM) is used to generate a 3D surface model from multiple 2D images. This step reconstructs the 3D geometry by identifying and matching feature points across images taken from different viewpoints. Second, we proceed with crack detection, where the curvature of the surface is analysed to identify potential cracks. The highest-curvature points are extracted based on a statistical threshold. Finally, a post-processing step is applied to refine the detected cracks. Binary dilation is used to expand the segmentation, ensuring that all damaged regions are identified accurately. Visualisation techniques are used to highlight the detected cracks, enabling

clear evaluation and interpretation. In combination, these steps enable an accurate and automated analysis of surface damage in wall paintings. The outlined steps of the proposed algorithm are explained in greater detail in the following, with its corresponding flowchart presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the presented methodology.

3.1. Structure from Motion

The input for the SfM process consists of images capturing wall paintings. SfM is a photogrammetric technique that is used to derive 3D structures from sequences of 2D images, often incorporating local motion indicators. Three preliminary steps are performed before executing the core SfM process. The first step involves feature extraction, where key points are identified in each image based on properties that remain consistent across scale and rotation. These features serve as the basis for determining the relative spatial position of the cameras. The second step is image matching, in which the corresponding key points in different images are identified by comparing and aligning their feature attributes. The final stage of initialisation refines these feature correspondences across multiple image pairs, enabling the later reconstruction of a 3D structure from the associated 2D points. The core SfM process begins once initialisation is complete. Matched key points from different images are combined into sequences, where each sequence represents a potential 3D point that is observable from multiple camera perspectives. These tracks are then used to estimate both the camera calibration parameters and the 3D structure of the scene, ultimately resulting in a sparse 3D reconstruction. The generated output from the first step is a dense 3D surface [19].

3.2. Crack Detection

In the second step, the normals are estimated for each point, using a KD-tree search to understand the local surface and to analyse variations in geometry [20]. The surface irregularity is then computed based on the deviation of the normals, serving as an indicator of surface anomalies. To identify cracks, a statistical threshold is applied, whose function is to identify the most curved points as potential cracks. This approach ensures that cracks are distinguished from natural surface variations, improving the accuracy of crack detection.

3.3. Post-processing

A post-processing step involving binary dilation is applied to improve the accuracy of crack detection [21]. This technique expands the initially detected cracks systematically by incorporating adjacent points, allowing a more complete representation of the degraded areas. By extending the segmented regions, this process ensures that fine and fragmented cracks, which might otherwise be missed, are included in the analysis. In addition, binary dilation helps smooth the detected boundaries, reducing noise, and improving the overall coherence of crack segmentation. The final visualisation highlights the cracks in red, providing a clear representation of their distribution across the surface.

4. Results

The wall paintings used in the analysis in this study were documented at the Church of the Annunciation of Mary in Crngrob, Škofja Loka, Slovenia. The selected wall painting features Saint Christopher, and is located on the western wall of the bell tower, dating back to the 19th century. Data acquisition was carried out using a DJI Matrice 300 RTK drone equipped with an RGB camera [22]. A selection of the captured images is presented in Fig. 2. The results in the continuation were produced on an AMD Ryzen 7 8840U 8-core processor with 64 GB of main memory on Windows 11.

Fig. 2: Sample images used for the SfM process.

Fig. 3 consists of three sections that illustrate some of the workflow steps and the results of the crack detection methodology applied to the selected wall painting. In Fig. 3a we can observe the entire reconstructed 3D model of the wall painting after the SfM process. This serves as the foundation for the analysis in step two by providing a detailed spatial representation of the painting. Fig. 3b highlights a zoomed-in section of the original 2D image captured using a drone. The red square represents the position of the zoomed-in section. This segment shows the raw visual data as they were recorded before any processing, illustrating the texture and surface conditions of the painting. Fig. 3c displays the same zoomed-in section (as in Fig. 3b) after the application of crack detection. By comparing Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c, it is evident that the areas highlighted in green in Fig. 3c correspond accurately to the cracks visible in the original image shown in Fig. 3b. This alignment highlights the accuracy of the crack detection process in identifying actual surface damage, starting from the creation of the 3D model to the application of crack detection, and provides visual evidence of the method's capability in identifying surface damage.

Fig. 3: Results of the crack detection process applied to a wall painting, where (a) is a 3D reconstructed model of the wall painting after the SfM process, (b) represents a zoomed-in section of the original 2D image captured by the drone, showing surface details, and, finally, (c) shows the same zoomed-in section after crack detection, with the cracks highlighted in green.

5. Conclusion

This paper proposes a comprehensive methodology for detecting cracks on 3D-reconstructed surfaces of wall paintings, combining SfM techniques with curvature-based crack detection, post-processing and visualisation. Using drone-acquired images and SfM, a precise 3D model of the wall painting surface was generated, enabling a non-invasive approach to surface analysis. The following curvature analysis identified high-curvature regions corresponding to surface anomalies effectively, while post-processing through binary

dilation ensured accurate segmentation of crack regions. The results demonstrate that the proposed method can detect and visualise cracks reliably, as validated by the correspondence between the detected cracks and the visible damage in the original images (see Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c). This workflow not only automates the detection process, but also improves the precision of structural damage evaluation, making it a valuable tool for long-term monitoring and conservation planning of cultural heritage sites. One of the main advantages of this approach is its ability to operate in a fully automated manner, reducing the need for manual intervention and ensuring consistency in crack detection results. Furthermore, the method is highly scalable, allowing efficient crack detection on large-scale surfaces without compromising accuracy. Using curvature-based detection, the method minimises false positives by differentiating actual cracks from natural surface variations, improving detection precision. In addition, further optimisations in the post-processing stage, including advanced filtering techniques, could improve the clarity and accuracy of detected cracks, ensuring even greater reliability in heritage conservation applications. Future work will focus on integrating additional data sources, such as thermal imaging and hyperspectral analysis, to improve the robustness of the method and expand its applicability to a wider range of surface conditions.

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7. References

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